

Methodology of Social and Cultural Adaptation of Students During Extracurricular Activities

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Abstract: In this article, in the process of out-of-class activities, the method of implementation of social and cultural adaptation of students and the emergence of the process of improving communicative competence with personality development, the theoretical foundations of socialization of students and the formation of a culture of social behavior in collective relations, from a socio-cultural point of view comments on modern approaches to the problem of educating the young generation are presented.

Key words: sociality, communicativeness, competence, team, positive, virtue, society, negative attitude, education, competence, upbringing, behavior, activity, manners.

Social competence is the newly emerging generalized socially interconnected qualities of a person, which are necessary aspects for successful performance of social roles and effective activity in the conditions of society and this society. Accordingly, social competences of a future pedagogue mean necessary and effective qualities during professional pedagogical activity, social pedagogical and social psychological knowledge, skill, skill, and method of activity. The competence approach shows the need to be introduced as a methodological component in determining the content of pedagogical education programs. The work of future teachers is essentially social, and that is why social competences are at the top during their work. Based on this, it can be said that social competence is created on the basis of professional pedagogical competence and forms a priority component of the student's personal qualities model, which includes individual personal characteristics.

Extracurricular activities allow students to move freely and show their potential in terms of the absence of specific standards, order, time and opportunity restrictions. Also, the collective nature of the tasks given to students serves to strengthen mutual relations in the team and the development of students' cultural communication skills.

In our study, we aimed to use the following types of extracurricular activities:

1. Excursion.
2. Spiritual and educational event.
3. Arrangements for furnishing the room.

During excursions and walks, it is necessary to organize observations of students' activities and teach children to perceive, think and feel.

"Tourists" game

The game "Tourists" is a long-term activity organized by the teacher, and students travel to neighboring countries and Uzbekistan. The most obvious advantage is in the travel game itself. After the children

themselves have chosen the theme of the trip, the teacher helps to organize the game, emphasizing that it is not a random choice for the students. The content of the game will be as follows: some of the students will play the role of tourists, travelers, and the other part will play the role of citizens of the country where the tourists came. The teacher who organized the game asks questions: "Who will sing Uzbek folk songs for tourists?" or "Who makes the toys?" etc. In the process of gathering knowledge, students should pay attention to each other's interest. Only then will they answer the teacher's questions correctly and reasonably. "This work can be done by Olima." "It can be made by the Wave" and others.

The teacher confirms the suggestions or mentions them if he notices other interests of the child. "But Komila performs Uzbek folk dances well. It would be good if he willingly prepares to present the dances to tourists."

Thus, in the process of actively discussing the emotional state of the child, the teacher's instructions help to compare the partners in the game, transfer their experiences to themselves. For this, the observers reveal the unique emotional state of the student. "I'm worried about Komila, she dances very well, but now she's upset, because none of the children wanted to dance with her in pairs, they were all busy making toys for tourists. Some of the children seem to be upset during the game and express their opinions as follows: "I don't like it, because the game should be fun and attractive for everyone" and so on.

However, this method is not always used, because in some children it reduces initiative, they wait for adults to speak or give advice. From time to time, the teacher expresses doubts about the success of the student team, allows students to defend their team, justify their proposals and analyze existing relationships.

The peak of the joint activity will be the plot of "welcoming tourists". After preparing, the students invited the travelers to a concert, to buy a souvenir, and to listen to a fairy tale. After the tourists paid their respects to the performers or masters, the teacher once again focused on the individual contributions of the children. "How can you not like the way Camila dances?" "The tool always does something unusual, so that everyone is surprised" and so on. The realization of shared joy and uniqueness protects the student from selfishness and individuality, creates an environment saturated with expectations of others, besides personal achievements, creates observation, sympathy, goodwill and mutual support.

Methodology of the game "Travel around the world".

The plot of the game is based on the students' knowledge about the near and far foreign countries and the planet Earth.

The teacher asks the students which country they would like to visit and invites them to travel around the world. It determines who wants to be a tourist and who wants to represent the country. The teacher said that tourists get to know the country, listen to songs and fairy tales, and those who want to represent their country wear national costumes and show products and products created by national masters.

The episodes "Journey to Uzbekistan" and "Journey to Africa" may leave the most vivid impression on the formation of the game. Students' travel to Uzbekistan is determined by choosing the city of Samarkand as the city to travel to, as it is a neighboring region. Here, students are traditionally introduced to this city in detail, introduce them to historical places, and provide historical information.

The teacher distributes pictures to the students, taking into account the previously identified interests and abilities. Pupils engaged in the same activity pair up and start training by joining groups. In this way, the teacher's role of organizing interaction in small groups is realized, the manifestation of the students' emotional state, and the feeling of the mood of their companions.

Methodology of organizing and conducting the event "Equipping the group room".

"Equipping the group room" is one of the formative activities aimed at developing observational and generalist students. The desire to be able to express oneself in collective relations is manifested not in specific activities, but in any case and in the aesthetics, accuracy, detail, and careful consideration of the

details of the result.

Having identified students with such a tendency, the teacher suggests how to equip the classroom and how to organize the work so that the members of the team feel comfortable. The event is organized outside of school hours, when regular activities are canceled, especially when walking time is reduced due to weather or precipitation.

Used literature

1. Vakhobov M.M. Introduction of state education standards based on the competence approach - as a paradigm of modern education. /Modern education/ *Sovremennoe obrazovanie*. Issue 10 of 2016, p. 3.
2. Basics of pedagogical competence and creativity / Muslimov N.A., Usmanboyeva M.H., Sayfurov D.M., Torayev A.B. — Tashkent, 2015. — 94 pages.
3. Зимняя И.А. Ключевые компетентности — новая парадигма результата образования // *Высшее Образование сегодня*. — 2003. - № 5.
4. *Общая и профессиональная педагогика* / Под ред. В.Д. Симоненко. - М., 2005. С.24